

THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN REAL ESTATE VALUATION

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Annotation. This article is devoted to the role of artificial intelligence in real estate valuation and the possibilities of its use in managing the urban environment to achieve sustainable urban development.

Keywords. Artificial intelligence, real estate valuation, urban planning concepts, sustainable development goals, ecological urban environment.

The price per square meter of property has been and remains a key factor in decisions about purchasing real estate. The sustainable urban development agenda for Uzbekistan's residential real estate market sets an important goal: by 2024, a total of more than 40 million square meters of buildings and structures will be built in our country. In general, it is planned to build 100 "New Uzbekistan" estates by 2030. For this, land will be allocated 1-2 kilometers from the district center or city area with a population of at least 70 thousand people. In each of these estates, 2 thousand apartments with an area of 100 thousand square meters will be built. This year, it is planned to build 120 thousand apartment buildings in our country. It is also planned to build 15 thousand apartments in New Tashkent. These houses will use "green" energy. To ensure energy sustainability, a 100-megawatt-hour electricity storage capacity will be installed on a private partnership basis.

Heating and cooling of houses in New Tashkent will be provided by a centralized "triple generation" system. Due to this, electricity consumption in the summer season will be reduced by 4 times. High energy efficiency requirements will be introduced for all buildings and structures. Transport, lighting systems and charging stations will be based only on "green" technologies.

In particular, 2,044 multi-storey buildings with more than 100,000 apartments have been built. Improving the housing conditions of at least 5 million families per year and increasing housing construction by at least 120 million square meters per year. At the same time, it is necessary to minimize the negative impact on the climate and the environment, since, according to scientific studies, cities consume 78% of the world's energy and produce more than 60% of greenhouse gas emissions.

Meeting modern requirements and standards for urban life creates the necessary conditions for the creation and implementation of new urban planning

concepts, as well as for increasing the value of real estate. The purpose of this article is to identify the prospects for the development of artificial intelligence in real estate valuation, taking into account the standards of current urban planning concepts.

In recent history, over the past 30 years, urban planning has been gradually developing. At the same time, the well-being of urban residents is increasing, they are filling their streets and courtyards with cars, apartments and offices with household appliances and computers, and business is expanding its production capacity. According to statistics, 40% of the world's raw materials are used in the construction of buildings, and the continued use of these buildings without the introduction of new energy-saving technologies can accelerate the generation of waste and environmental pollution. Therefore, when assessing real estate, special attention is paid to factors characterizing the ecological state of the urban environment.

Due to the large number of pricing factors, appraisers are faced with the need to use the results of large database analyses. Therefore, artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly gaining recognition in appraisal activities, which helps to objectively assess the strengths and weaknesses of the object and find the most effective solutions. The main advantage of AI in real estate appraisal is its ability to quickly and efficiently analyze a huge amount of data, which the human mind is not capable of. Machine learning is developing in various fields to analyze data from various sources, extract the necessary information and select the most appropriate information.

Appraisal companies are taking the first steps in the application of artificial intelligence (various software, blockchain, neural networks). In practice, bottom-up AI is used, where it is developed based on existing databases and experience, and AI also provides for the prediction of property values. However, recently, so-called top-down AI, which is fully programmable by humans (creation of expert systems, knowledge bases and logical inference systems), has begun to be used.

In general, the use of artificial intelligence has enormous potential to increase the accuracy, speed and accessibility of assessments. It can be concluded that these technologies will make the entire real estate appraisal process more objective, since technological advances will allow for faster assessments and increased transparency in the market, in particular, eliminating the phenomenon of intentional overpricing of real estate prices by agents.

The development of artificial intelligence in real estate valuation is facilitated by the implementation of modern urban planning concepts that are

consistent with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Their implementation mechanisms are largely consistent and are elements of the “green agenda” for global development. The main goal of AI training is to expand the list of pricing factors for real estate valuation.

The concept of green building defines a fundamentally new state policy on the use of new, highly efficient technologies and materials for housing construction. The state develops new laws in accordance with the design of energy-efficient housing and develops building codes and regulations. These standards help to bring the occupancy and subsequent operation of new buildings into line with the standards set by the SDGs.

The concept of a closed-loop (circular) economy includes a number of fundamentally new approaches to the rational use of resources in construction based on renewable construction solutions: recycling and reuse of construction and demolition waste; prevention of building collapse and appropriate technical control; the use of design methods that allow for the recycling of materials during demolition; designing buildings for future use for various purposes; and the use of prefabricated structures that reduce transportation costs during the dismantling of buildings, as well as reduce waste during demolition. The concept of increasing the energy efficiency of buildings also deserves attention.

The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 300 dated May 7, 2025 “On measures to accelerate projects aimed at increasing energy efficiency” was approved. The goal of the strategy is to adapt the economy to the global energy transition, reduce greenhouse gas emissions and achieve carbon neutrality with sustainable economic growth by 2030. The strategy includes measures for specific sectors: energy, industry, housing and utilities.

The World Economic Forum report notes that although it is difficult to determine the exact contribution of real estate to the greenhouse effect, it is nevertheless a significant energy consumer and carbon dioxide emitter. Based on modern urban planning concepts, AI can automate valuation processes and analyze deeper data, as well as identify hidden relationships and predict potential risks for real estate management. This increases the accuracy and reliability of valuation results.

Conclusions

Machine learning allows us to use various models and methods to predict real estate values, taking into account the implementation of state programs to support the construction industry and protect the interests of citizens in improving the standard of living in urban areas. Artificial intelligence can not only

solve the problems of preserving the urban environment in the current situation, but also provide strategic recommendations for its improvement. By analyzing data, artificial intelligence can identify the main factors affecting the cleanliness of air, water and soil. These factors can affect the future value of land for residential construction in urban settlements. This will help city leaders make more informed decisions when drawing up master plans for urban development.

Today, environmental monitoring systems based on artificial intelligence allow each city resident to obtain information about the environmental situation. Access to the Internet in cities and large settlements improves the quality of life and allows for informed decisions on urban development. This means that the development of artificial intelligence in real estate valuation reduces the risk of financial losses and increases the efficiency of investments in the development of new territories.

The development of artificial intelligence in real estate valuation opens up new prospects for innovation and new technologies in business. The use of artificial intelligence not only increases the accuracy and objectivity of the valuation process, but also creates new opportunities for all participants in the valuation process to make strategic decisions, effectively manage risks and urban planning in accordance with the main requirements of modern cities: ensuring public safety and a high quality of life, while preserving the natural environment and resources, and ensuring a balanced economic and social balance.

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